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Comparative analysis of teaching methods for large classes

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INTRODUCTION

Studying engineering has never been more popular and the societal need for engineering skills is immense. As a consequence, we are accepting more and better skilled students to many of our programmes and our classes have become larger and larger over the years. Large classes are defined in this study as classes of more than 100 students and up to a 1000 students. Teaching large classes and running laboratory training exercises with a great number of students poses a series of challenges that may hamper learning in general and specially that of high-skilled students in specific and hence these are important to address. These challenges include decreasing teacher-to-student dialogue, promoting student disengagement and erosion of sense of responsibility for learning [1][2].

As noted by Ramsden [3], “many lecturers in the 1980s handled classes of 30 to 50 students, they are now faced with groups in the hundreds. Widening participation means that today’s academics are also expected to deal with an unprecedentedly broad spectrum of student ability and background. They can no longer rely on students having detailed previous knowledge, especially in mathematics and science.”

More recently, Graham [4] identified delivering student-centered learning for large classes as one of the key future challenges in engineering education. However, little research has so far been performed with regard to what constitutes “good teaching” when it comes to large classes and little work has been done with regard to evaluating existing and innovative teaching methods (TM) when it comes to address the challenges that large classes pose.

In order to address these research needs, we first reviewed the literature on what constitutes good teaching and reflect upon identified criteria and their feasibility when it comes to large classes. Second, we identified TMs which traditionally have been used or proposed in the literature, including: lecture-based learning (LCL), team-based learning (TBL), problem-based learning (PBL) and a combination of lecture capturing and active learning exercises (LC/ALEx). TBL, PBL and LC/ALEx were selected as they are all represented by the consortium and thus have high priority to us and that they have all been proposed and frequently cited in the literature as alternative to conventional teaching or LCL. Furthermore, these innovative TMs may have potential for widespread implementation in university teaching. Third, we analyzed and evaluate each of the identified TMs up against the seven identified criteria for good teaching of large classes and we discuss the limitations of our study and how the pros of each method can, in theory, be used to optimize student learning. Finally, we provide a number of recommendations on how our findings can be further explored and validated. This paper is the first to complete a comparative analysis of innovative teaching methods across universities on three different continents, when it comes to addressing the specific challenges that teaching large classes pose and therein lies the novelty of our work.

1 CRITERIA FOR GOOD TEACHING

Putting forward criteria for what constitutes good teaching is challenging and arguably context and student dependent. When it comes to undergraduate teaching, Chickering and Gamson [5] has proposed seven principles of effective teaching: 1) Encourage contact between students and faculty in order to keep students motivated and involved; 2) Develop reciprocity and cooperation among students in order for the students to sharpen their cognitive process and promoted deeper learning; 3) Encourage active learning as passive students do not learn as effectively as active ones; 4) Provide prompt feedback as formative and summative feedback is key to support ongoing student learning; 5) Emphasis time on task in order for the students to develop time-management skills; 6) Communicate high expectations in order to motivate to expend an extra effort to meet these expectations; and 7) Respect diverse talents and ways of learning acknowledging that all student and unique and required a variety of learning experiences to facilitate their learning.

Acknowledging that there is “no best” to teach, Ramsden [3] has similarly proposed thirteen important properties of good teaching: 1) A desire to share your love of the subject with students; 2) An ability to make the material being taught stimulating and interesting; 3) A facility for engaging with students at their level of understanding; 4) A capacity to explain the material plainly; 5) A commitment to making it absolutely clear what has to be understood at what level and why; 6) Showing concern and respect for students; 7) A commitment to encouraging independence; 8) An ability to improvise and adapt to new demands; 9) Using teaching methods and academic tasks that require students to learn actively, responsibly and co-operatively; 10) Using valid assessment methods; 11) A focus on key concepts, and students misunderstandings of them, rather than covering the ground; 12) Giving the highest quality feedback on student work; and 13) A desire to learn from students and other sources about the effects of teaching and how it can be improved.

Obviously, there is some overlap or alignment between the principles proposed by Chickering and Gamson [5] and the properties put forward by Ramsden [3]. For instance, Ramsden’s “showing concern and respect for student” and “using TMs and academic tasks that require students to learn thoughtfully, responsibly, and cooperatively” are similar to Chickering and Gamson’s “respects diverse talents and ways of learning” and “develop reciprocity and cooperation among students” [6]. The importance and relevance of many of the criteria put forward by Chickering and Gamson [5] and Ramsden [3] are independent of the size of a given class e.g. having a desire to share your love of the subject with students. *Table 1* provides an overview of the seven criteria for good teaching identified in this study as the most relevant for consider when it comes to teaching large classes. The seven criteria address a series of didactic issues relevant for teaching in general and especially for large classes. However, they do not address issues related to resources, economy and the overall feasibility of the TMs. To account for this, three additional criteria were added, *Table 2*, dealing with instructor and technical resources required and the flexibility with respect to facilities.

Table 1. Criteria for good teaching practices in large classes independent of teaching form, the rationale behind including the criteria and the references for why the criteria are important to the comparison and evaluation of large class teaching.

Criteria	Rationale for including criteria and references for why the criteria are important.
1. Encourage contact between students and faculty.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Student-faculty interactions within and out of classes promote student commitment and motivation [5] [7]. - Faculty members serve as inspiration and as partner of discussion improving the aspiration of the students [3] [5] [8]. - Learning requires cooperation between student and faculty. Enhanced student-faculty contact promotes the cooperation [9].
2. Promote student collaboration and responsibility for own learning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After graduation students will enter jobs where team-work-skills are often a requirement or at least appreciated [10]. - Collaboration promotes corporative learning [3] [11]. - Students learn from each other and learn from teaching each other [3] [12].
3. Promote active learning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active learning is one of the major keystones assuring high academic gains [3] [5] [12] [13] [14].
4. Meet diverse ways of learning.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students do not learn the same way and they bring in different competences to learn. To meet these diverse ways of learning the educators must facilitate various styles of teaching so that all students have the opportunity to learn within their comfort zones but challenge themselves by learning in new ways [3] [5] [9].
5. Promote critical thinking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The literature is in consensus that the development of critical thinking is a vital skill for students. Students which master critical thinking have greater success in education and career and are of much more importance to society [3] [15].
6. Gives prompt feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students need to know what they do not know in order to focus their learning [3] [5] [7].
7. Provide structure and guidance with respect time management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structure helps students to recognize and improve deep learning [16]. - Students need help to learn effective time management [5].

Table 2. Other criteria important for the feasibility of the teaching methods

Criteria	Rationale for including criteria
8. Need for instructor resources allocated.	With large classes, the TMs require a lot with respect to instructor time allocated per student e.g. feedback, grading of assignments. This criterion assesses the overall instructor workload.
9. Need for technical resources allocated.	The technical feasibility of the TMs must be assessed. Does the approach require advanced technology? This criterion evaluates the economical investments required for the teaching approach to be feasible.
10. Flexibility with respect to facilities.	From an administrative point of view it is important to assess if the teaching approaches are tied to specific facilities. e.g. special class room features. This criterion assesses how likely it is to apply the teaching approach at any given location.

2 TEACHING METHODS

A range of different TMs have been proposed in the literature. In our analysis we included TMs which traditionally have been proposed as alternative to conventional teaching and which may have potential for widespread use in university teaching.

2.1 Lecture-based learning

The terms “conventional teaching” or LBL are not well-defined and are used for many different teaching approaches [17]. In this paper we define LBL as TMs which are educator-centred rather than student-centred and which are based primarily on lectures. The teaching approaches applied are often deductive of nature and a typical example would be an educator that prepares and presents the course curricula in shorter or longer lectures, broken into smaller sessions where students are activated by various exercises. In LBL communication is mainly one-directional but do offers possibilities for students to raise their hands and ask questions.

2.2 Problem-based learning

PBL was developed within medical education in the late sixties to face the problem that medical knowledge and new technologies constantly emerged [18]. The teaching approach places the student learning process in focus and students in small groups are confronted with a problem provided by the facilitator rather than with theory and exercises [19]. Barrows [20] describes six core elements of PBL. 1) Learning is student-centred, 2) Learning occurs in small groups, 3) Teachers are facilitators or guides, 4) Problems form the organizing focus and stimulus for learning, 5) Problems are vehicle for the development of problem-solving skills, and 6) New information is acquired through self-directed learning. PBL comes in various designs and with very different facilitator approaches [20] [21]. In its most pristine form, the students are presented to the “case of concern” with no further introduction. The task of the students is then to decipher the problem and the nature of it, derive a solution to the identified problem and implement the solution. In other approaches the facilitator might introduce key concepts before introducing the problem [21] or cut away or emphasize some of the learning tasks.

2.3 Team-based learning

TBL was developed at the University of Oklahoma in the late seventies to meet the challenge of increasing enrolment. It is an instructional method where the students, in small teams, apply conceptual knowledge following a three phases protocol [22]. Phase I is an individual pre-class study, where the students familiarize themselves with the knowledge needed for solving in-class challenges. Phase II is a readiness assurance test (RAT) consisting of an individual readiness assurance test (iRAT) and a team readiness assurance test (tRAT). First, the students complete the iRAT which typically is a multiple choice test. Then the students complete the tRAT by answering the same test as a group getting immediate feedback. In phase III, the facilitator can bring up issues identified by the RAT and the students can ask questions before the teams apply the knowledge gained in a decision-based exercise. Classical TBL holds seven core elements: 1) Team formation; 2) RATs; 3) Immediate feedback systems; 4) In-class team-based problem solving; 5) Application of the 4S-principle (**S**ignificant problem; **A**t a given time working at the **S**ame problem; **S**pecific choice and **S**imultaneous report); 6) Structure; and 7) Peer review [23].

2.4 Lecture capturing and active learning exercises

LC dates as far back as 1970 and is defined as “an umbrella term” that covers any technology that allows instructors to record, and make available instructional activities in their classrooms. The term is used to describe the use of software and hardware options which allow for a wide range of capabilities ranging from a simple podcasts (audio recordings) to more complex systems that allow students to personalize lecture capture by tagging, editing, annotating, and subsequently sharing the results with their peers [24]. LC can be both synchronous and asynchronous. Synchronous lecture capture occurs when the capture is live broadcast allowing remote students to be in sync with the local lectures. Asynchronous lecture capture is the recording of lectures and making those recordings available to the remote students after the local lecture is complete. Traditionally both versions of LC were lecturer-centered and a one-way conversation. More recently LC technologies have advanced to allow remote students to post questions during the recording and thereby interact with the lecturer and fellow student [25]. LC is often said to make out-of-class learning more productive but it is not intended to be used as a replacement for in-class instruction [26]. Instead the aim is to assist in making face-to-face class time more appealing [24] [25] [27] and to support students whose first language is not the language of instruction. ALEx or active learning activities (ALA) is an instructional method where pre-planned activities make the students put to use the content that they have just been taught. Many different ALA and ALEx exist [27] [28] which are either informal or graded.

3 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LBL, PBL, TBL AND LC/ALEX

In the final part of our study, we assessed the fulfilment of the various criteria for each of the four TMs on a scale going from “high”, “medium” to “low” (see *Table 3*). The assessment was done on basis of the literature review and is a qualitative reflection of the authors’ perspectives. In general, LBL scores low with regards to all identified criteria except for “providing structure and guidance with respect to time management” (High) and “flexibility with respect to facilities” (Medium). This is due to the fact that LBL is a teacher-centered one-directional TM which per definition is everything which modern innovative teaching is moving away from. However, it does hold some advantages like structure and limited resources allocation needed. PBL and TBL both scored medium with regard to “encouraging contacts between students and faculty” and high on: “promoting student collaboration and responsibility for own learning”; “promoting active learning; meeting diverse ways of learning”; “promote critical thinking”; and “need for instructor resources allocated”. Whereas TBL scored high and medium on “giving prompt feedback” and “providing structure and guidance with respect time management”, where PBL scored low on both. Whereas PBL scored low and high on the “need for technical resources allocated” and “flexibility with respect to facilities”, respectively, it was vice versa for TBL. The similarities in our evaluation of PBL and TBL are that they build upon many of the same key elements [19] [20] [22] [23]. Most importantly, both TMs are conducted in small teams which encourage collaboration, active learning, diverse learning approaches and critical thinking. The differences in our evaluation of PBL and TBL are due to the fact that TBL has incorporated direct feedback mechanisms in a repeated structure [22] and that it requires a substantial technical investment making TBL a rather non-flexible TM [29]. LC/ALEx scores medium for all criteria except for “providing structure and guidance with respect time management” and “need for instructor resources allocated” where it scores high and for “flexibility with respect to facilities” where it scores low. LC/ALEx

is an improved version of LBL which require a lot of instructor resources in terms of teaching assistants and technical resources in terms of LC-devices and large lecture halls. The lecture hall requirements make LBL non-flexible with respect to facilities.

Table 3. Comparative assessment of the four teaching methods according to the identified criteria.

Criteria	LBL	PBL	TBL	LC/ALEX
1. Encourages contacts between students and faculty.	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
2. Promote student collaboration and responsibility for own learning.	Low	High	High	Medium
3. Promote active learning.	Low	High	High	Medium
4. Meet diverse ways of learning.	Low	High	High	Medium
5. Promote critical thinking.	Low	High	High	Medium
6. Gives prompt feedback.	Medium	Low	High	Medium
7. Provide structure and guidance with respect time management	High	Low	Medium	High
a. Need for instructor resources allocated.	Low	High	High	High
b. Need for technical resources allocated.	Low	Low	High	Medium
c. Flexibility with respect to facilities.	Medium	High	Low	Low

4 DISCUSSION

In this study, we set out to identify criteria for good teaching of large classes and compare these criteria up against features of traditionally used TMs and more recently proposed innovative TMs. Overall, we found that each of the analyzed TMs have pros and cons from a theoretical point of view. When considering our findings, it is important to have a number of aspects in mind. First of all, it is well acknowledged that there are not universally accepted criteria for what good teaching is and that good teaching is always context and student dependent [3] [30]. On the one hand, it seems that there are criteria for good teaching that are independent of the size of the class, e.g. clear communication with respect to expectations, guidance, feedback and evaluation, efficient announcement of high expectations to the students and securing of a good learning environment, where the students feel safe and where they are not afraid of “failing” [3] [5]. On the other hand, we have identified 7 criteria that we believe are influenced by the size of the class, but we might have overlooked important criteria and more research is needed to explore variation in preferences and criteria among broad spectrum of students and teachers considering their diverse abilities and backgrounds [3]. Second, it is important to remember that the TMs that we analyzed in this study are selected because they have been proposed in the literature and because they have potential for widespread implementation in university teaching. This does not mean that there might not be innovative TMs that we have not considered and should have included in our analysis e.g. flipped classroom and project-based learning. Furthermore, there are many variations of the TMs that we did not include in our analysis and it cannot be ruled out that variations of e.g. PBL have been developed in order to address the limitations that we have identified in our analysis. More work is needed in order to consider these and similar aspects. Finally, our evaluation of the four different TMs up against the seven criteria that we identified as important when it comes to teaching large classes is arguable theoretical and could

be more empirically based. For instance, application of the different TMs in the same teacher and discipline settings and with similar students with regard to ability and background could provide a basis for which to explore the hypotheses that we have generated with our analysis.

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